

QSAR study on the inhibition of the human carbonic anhydrase cytosolic isozyme hCA VII[†]

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Abstract : Quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) has been established for 21 phenacetyl-, pyridylacetyl- and thienylacetyl-substituted aromatic and heterocyclic sulfonamides including 4 clinically used derivatives (ethaoxazolamide, acetazolamide, zonisamide and topiramate) against inhibitory activity of a newly cloned human carbonic anhydrase (CA, EC 4.2.1.1) isozyme hCA VII. A heuristic algorithm selects the best multiple linear regression (MLR) equation showed the correlation between the observed values and the estimated values of activity is very good ($N = 21$, $Se = 0.1076$, $r^2 = 0.9311$, $r^2_{CV} = 0.9181$, $F = 128.3036$). With a view to external validation, the calibration set includes 15 molecules and the validation set includes 6 molecules. Identification of molecules in validation set with high estimated value of inhibitory activity of hCA VII is correct enough to have practical value. The virtual molecular fragments that lead to a significant increase of the inhibitory activity of hCA VII are CH_3 ($r = 0.633$), C_7H_3NSO ($r = 0.4872$), O atom ($r = 0.4586$) and decrease the inhibitory activity of hCA VII is C_7H_4NO ($r = -0.7231$).

Keywords : Sulfonamides, carbonic anhydrase inhibitor, hCA VII, QSAR, PRECLAV.

Introduction

The ubiquitous metalloenzymes carbonic anhydrase (CAs, EC 4.2.1.1) catalyze the inter-conversion between carbon dioxide and the bicarbonate ion at the physiological pH^{1,2}. The human carbonic anhydrase (CA, EC 4.2.1.1) isozyme is inhibited by aromatic and heterocyclic sulfonamides^{3,4}, the classical CA inhibitors with clinical applications². These enzymes are inhibited by aromatic and heterocyclic sulphonamides, among which acetazolamide represents the prototype of a class of pharmacological agents with apparently limited therapeutic usefulness nowadays, but which played a major role in the development of fundamental renal physiology and pharmacology, as well as for the design of many of the presently widely used diuretic agents, such as among others the thiazide and high ceiling diuretics²⁻⁷. In mammals, 16 different α -CA isozymes or CA-related proteins (CARP) were described so far, with very different catalytic activity, sub-cellular localization, tissue distribution and susceptibility to be inhibited by sulfonamides^{1-4,6,7}. Basically, there are several cytosolic forms (CA I-III, CA

VII), five membrane-bound isozymes (CA IV, CA IX, CA XII, CA XIV and CA XV), two mitochondrial forms (CA VA and VB), as well as one secreted CA isozyme CA VI. The catalytic isozymes (CARPs) are CA VIII, CA X and CA XI²⁻⁷. These enzymes are involved in crucial physiological processes connected with respiration and transport of CO_2 /bicarbonate between metabolizing tissues and lungs, pH and CO_2 homeostasis, electrolyte secretion in a variety of tissues/organs, biosynthetic reactions (such as gluconeogenesis, lipogenesis and ureagenesis), boneresorption, calcification, tumorigenicity and many other physiologic/pathologic processes²⁻⁸.

The hCA VII shows a rather limited distribution only in some organs/tissues, such as the brain for hCA VII⁸. The involvement of the cytosolic isoform hCA VII in the neuronal excitation showed its inhibition as a possible antiepileptic mechanism^{9,10}. Furthermore, some clinically used drugs, such as acetazolamide (AZA), zonisamide (ZNS) and topiramate (TPM)[†] (Comp. no. 19-21 in Table 1), also show anticonvulsant activity and are used as antiepileptic drugs.

[†]In honour of Professor Padmakar V. Khadikar.

Scheme 1. Structure of new sulfonamides (A-D) and 4 clinically used sulfonamides/sulphamate (EZA-TPM).

In view of the above, the aim of this investigation is to use the MOPAC¹¹ and PRECLAV¹² software for the identification of statistically significant QSAR models and significant molecular virtual fragments to design and develop potent carbonic anhydrase hCA VII inhibitor. Quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) studies find the physicochemical parameters of the compounds that govern their biological activity and throws light on their mechanism of action.

Methods and computational details :

In this paper, I present the results of two QSAR studies performed with the PRECLAV computer program. The starting point of the computation was the database of 21 derivatives of phenacetyl-, pyridylacetyl- and thienylacetyl-substituted aromatic and heterocyclic sulfonamides including some of the clinically used derivatives (ethoxzolamide, acetazolamide, zonisamide, and topiramate) shown in Table 1, were included in the cali-

Table 1. Structural details of hCA VII inhibitor and their observed inhibitory activities ($-\log K_I$)

Compd. no.	See structure above	n	Y	X_1	X_2	$-\log K_I$
1*	A	0	H	-	-	-0.792
2	A	0	F	-	-	-0.845
3	A	0	Cl	-	-	-0.839
4*	A	0	Br	-	-	-0.857
5	A	1	H	-	-	-0.851
6*	A	2	H	-	-	-0.881
7	B	-	-	-	-	-0.839
8	C	0	H	CH	CH	-0.672
9	C	1	H	CH	CH	-0.833
10	C	2	H	CH	CH	-0.74
11	C	0	F	CH	CH	-0.732
12	C	0	Cl	CH	CH	-0.839
13	C	0	Br	CH	CH	-0.724
14	C	0	H	N	CH	-0.886
15	C	0	H	CH	N	-0.898
16*	C	2	H	CH	N	-0.929
17	D	-	-	CH	CH	-0.785
18	EZA	-	-	-	-	0.097
19*	AZA	-	-	-	-	-0.398
20	ZNS	-	-	-	-	-2.068
21*	TPM	-	-	-	-	0.046

Index with asterisk * molecules of validation set.

bration set. The inhibition data (as K_I values, in the nanomolar range for isozymes) as reported by Ozlen Guzel *et al.*¹³ have been used after converting them into negative logarithmic units i.e. as $-\log K_I$ (hCA VII), and the experimental data are presented in Table 1.

The virtual constructions of the molecules and geometry optimization have been done using the Molecular Mechanics force field MM+ of HyperChem software¹⁴. The MM+ force field is an extension of latest MM2 force field which was developed by Allinger and co-workers^{15,16}. The conformations of minimum energy obtained by molecular mechanics calculations were further minimized by quantum chemical calculations. The semi empirical PM6 method¹⁷ included in the MOPAC¹¹ 2007 software (Stewart Computational Chemistry, Colorado Springs, CO) optimized the geometry more rigorously. The output file from MOPAC was used as input file for PRECLAV program^{12,18,19}. Using these data, PRECLAV calculated for each molecule the values for almost 300

quantum chemical descriptors, specific for this program. The statistical calculations used for obtaining the QSAR equations were done again with PRECLAV, as reported earlier²⁰⁻²⁶.

The program has used only "significant" descriptors in calculating the QSAR equations, descriptors that fulfill criteria

$$r^2 > 0.005 \quad (1)$$

where, r^2 is the square of the Pearson linear correlation between the values of the analyzed descriptor and the values of the dependent property.

The program combines successively sets with 2, 3, k significant descriptors ($1 < k < 11$). A set of descriptors contains only descriptors that are sufficiently low intercorrelated and fulfill criteria (2).

$$r_{ij}^2 < N^{-1/2} \quad (2)$$

where r_{ij}^2 is the square of Pearson linear correlation between the values of two descriptors present in the same set, N is the number of molecules in the calibration set (here $N = 21$).

Each set of descriptors has been used to calculate a multilinear QSAR equation of type (3).

$$A = C_0 + \sum_{i=2}^k C_i \cdot D_i \quad (3)$$

where, A is $-\log(K_I)$ the dependent property (here the inhibitory activity defined above), C_0 is the free term (intercept), C_i are the coefficients (weighting factors) of the descriptors, D_i are some significant descriptors and k is the number of descriptors in the set.

The C_i coefficients have been calculated with OLSM (Ordinary Least Square Method). Thousands of equations of type (3) were this calculated. With each of the type (3) equation, the values of inhibitory activity (A) were calculated, which were compared to the observed activity. The agreement between the calculated/observed inhibitory activity was measured using the cross-validation function Q , specific to the employed program¹² which possesses values in the interval $[-1, 1]$.

$$Q = r_{CV}^2 \cdot (N - k)/N \quad (4)$$

where, r_{CV}^2 is cross-validated (Leave one out method) Pearson square linear correlation between computed/observed values.

By increasing the number of descriptors k , the quality Q of the equations increases, reaches a maximum, and then decreases. For predictions, the equation with the highest quality was used, the descriptors present in this equation being called 'predictors'. The value of the predictors used in this study (QSAR-1) is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Value of the predictors used in QSAR-1 and QSAR-2

Compd. no.	SNU	XVC	ARC	XVC
1	-0.7401	-0.8893	-	-
2	-0.7508	-0.8777	-0.7195	-0.9231
3	-0.7607	-0.8822	-0.714	-0.9261
4	-0.772	-0.8913	-	-
5	-0.7924	-0.8531	-0.7152	-0.9034
6	-0.8128	-0.7515	-	-
7	-0.674	-0.7563	-0.9627	-0.8002
8	-0.7953	-0.8711	-0.7138	-0.9183
9	-0.7199	-0.9063	-0.7136	-0.9359
10	-0.6546	-0.8984	-0.715	-0.9343
11	-0.7086	-0.9177	-0.7144	-0.9319
12	-0.6366	-0.9222	-0.7138	-0.9238
13	-0.5065	-0.9087	-0.7713	-0.9359
14	-0.7888	-0.8287	-0.7773	-0.8803
15	-0.7878	-0.7778	-0.743	-0.8253
16	-0.6501	-0.8324	-	-
17	-0.6587	-0.8923	-0.7138	-0.7722
18	-0.62	-0.1123	-0.7186	0.0912
19	-0.5939	-0.7863	-	-
20	-1.9772	-0.9046	-2.0494	-0.9358
21	-0.8666	0.1926	-	-

SNU (percent of sulfur minimum charge for S atom at parabolic region)

XVC (maximum free valance of C atoms at parabolic region)

ARC (100-Average atomic one-electron reaction index for C atoms at parabolic region).

The relative utility of the predictors :

The program¹² calculates the relative utility (U) value of the predictors, using eq. (5)

$$U = (R^2 - r^2)/(1 - r^2) \quad (5)$$

where, R^2 is the square of the Pearson correlation between the experimental and calculated values of $-\log K_1$ (values calculated using an equation with p predictors), r^2 is the square of the Pearson correlation between the experimental and calculated values of $-\log K_1$ (values cal-

culated using an equation with $p-1$ predictors, that is the equation that does not contain the analyzed predictor).

After calculating the value of U for all the predictors, these values are normalized according to the highest U (the highest value becomes 1000). The predictors with a high value of U ($U > 400$) may be considered very useful in calculating the inhibitory activity. These predictors are useful as they correlate very well with $\log K_1$ and do not correlate with the other predictors. Each "useful" predictor explains (quite) a lot of the $-\log K_1$ variation and, in the same time, a different thing as the other predictors.

Identifying the significant virtual molecular fragments :

Computer assisted procedure for virtual fragmentation criteria are the bond order's value of the chemical bonds and the type of the connected atoms (hydrogen, carbon, and heteroatom). PRECLAV¹² divides the analyzed molecules into virtual fragments, using an algorithm reported earlier²⁷⁻²⁹. The virtual fragments identified by PRECLAV do not always coincide with the classical functional groups. The presence of a significant fragment in the molecule greatly influences (in a positive or negative way) the inhibitory activity of the molecule. Molecules of analyzed database include four significant virtual fragments given in Table 3.

Table 3. Significant molecular virtual fragments

Fragment atoms	Specimen compd. no.	Correlation	Fisher function (F)
C ₇ H ₄ NO	20	-0.7231	219.1
CH ₃	18	0.633	133.7
C ₇ H ₃ NSO	18	0.4872	62.2
O atom	21	0.4586	53.3

Correlation sign + means 'large mass percent of this fragment increase the property value'.

Correlation sign - means 'large mass percent of this fragment decrease the property value'.

Obtaining the homogenized calibration set :

All practical QSAR studies are faced with the problem of correctly identifying the outlier molecules in the calibration set. The presence of these molecules makes it difficult to obtain results with practical value. Correct identification of the molecular characteristics with high influence over the dependent property, very necessary in drug design.

The process of identifying and eliminating the outlier molecules precedes any other computation in “drug design” procedures. Consequently, the author has considered that QSAR studies (with or without a validation set) will lead to erroneous results if the calibration/validation sets contain outlier molecules. QSAR-1 studies shows that number of outlier is zero. The homogenized calibration set (21 molecules) has been obtained.

Validation of the computation procedure :

For the validation of the method, I have proceeded to a QSAR study with a validation set and reduced calibration set. The validation set was extracted from the homogenized calibration set. For the extraction, the molecules in this set have been ordered according to the observed value of hCA VII inhibitory activity, starting from the lowest values. For equal values, the order was arbitrary. In this set, the molecules with rank 21, 19, 1, 4, 6 and 16 have constituted the validation set. The remaining molecules form the reduced calibration set. I can assume that the reduced calibration set obtained in this way is a representative sample for the homogenized calibration set. The quality of the prediction for the validation set was considered a measure of the quality of the computation method. The external validation procedure presented here must not be mistaken with the LOO (Leave One Out) internal cross-validation method used by PRECLAV in various stages of the computation.

Results and discussion

I applied the PRECLAV algorithm in two QSAR studies, using the set of 1-21 hCA VII inhibitors, as shown in Table 1. The quality of the obtained equations is reflected by the value of the Q function and also by values of some usual statistical functions.

QSAR-1 :

Dependent property : hCA VII inhibitors

Descriptors used : Quantum chemical descriptor calculated by PRECLAV

Molecules number in calibration set : 21

Number of the significant descriptors : 61

$$C_0 = 0.7228$$

$$C_1 = 0.9676$$

D_1 = SNU (percent of sulfur•minimum charge for S

atom at parabolic region) ($U = 1000$)

$$C_2 = 0.9655$$

D_2 = XVC (maximum free valance of C atoms at parabolic region) ($U = 991$)

Whereas the quality of correlation is described by the statistical indices :

$$Se = 0.1076; r^2 = 0.9311; F = 128.3036; r^2_{CV} = 0.9181; Q = 0.8307$$

Se standard error of values, r^2 = Pearson square correlation, F = Fisher function, r^2_{CV} = Pearson cross-validated square correlation (Leave one out method), and Q = quality.

The intercorrelations between predictor is $r^2 = 0.0012$. The lowest correlation with hCA VII inhibitory activity is calculated for predictor XVC ($r^2 = 0.467$). Considering the values of Se , r^2 , r^2_{CV} and the estimative quality of hCA VII inhibitory activity is for the whole molecular set is very good. The high usability of predictor SNU (percent of sulfur•minimum charge for S atom, $U = 1000$) positive correlation shows that increase the percentage of sulfur and minimum charge for S atom is favorable to inhibitory activity. The another predictor XVC (maximum free valance of C atoms) positive correlation in the aforementioned model indicates that increase the maximum free valance of C atoms is favorable for the inhibitory activity. The percents, in weight, of some molecular fragments are well correlated (directly or inversely) with the values of inhibitory activity presented in Table 3. The presence of CH_3 (Compd. no. 18, 19, 21), C_7H_3NSO (compd. no. 18) and O atom (Compd. no. 21) fragments are favorable to the inhibitory activity. The presence of fragment C_7H_4NO (Compd. no. 20) is not favorable for the hCA VII inhibitory activity.

The observed and estimated activity ($-\log K_1$) and their residue are given in Table 4. The correlation of observed vs estimated activity are shown in Fig. 1. In the QSAR-1 estimated and observed $-\log K_1$ are very close to each other, thus, exhibiting the predictive power of the model.

Validation of the computational method :

Using the procedure described above a validation set of 6 molecules has been extracted from the homogenized calibration set. These molecules have been marked in Table 1 with asterisk* characters. The remaining mole-

Table 4. Observed and estimated activity using QSAR-1

Compd. no.	Obs.	Est.	Res.
1	-0.792	-0.852	0.06
2	-0.845	-0.851	0.006
3	-0.839	-0.865	0.026
4	-0.857	-0.885	0.028
5	-0.851	-0.868	0.017
6	-0.881	-0.789	-0.092
7	-0.839	-0.66	-0.179
8	-0.672	-0.888	0.216
9	-0.833	-0.849	0.016
10	-0.74	-0.778	0.038
11	-0.732	-0.849	0.117
12	-0.839	-0.784	-0.055
13	-0.724	-0.645	-0.079
14	-0.886	-0.841	-0.045
15	-0.898	-0.79	-0.108
16	-0.929	-0.71	-0.219
17	-0.785	-0.7776	-0.0074
18	0.097	0.014	0.083
19	-0.398	-0.611	0.213
20	-2.068	-2.064	-0.004
21	0.046	0.07	-0.024

Fig. 1. Correlation of observed and estimated activity for QSAR-1. molecules (15 molecules) have formed the reduced calibration set. The reduced set and the validation set have been used in QSAR-2 study.

QSAR-2 :

Dependent property : hCA VII inhibitors

Descriptors used : Quantum chemical descriptor calculated by PRECLAV

Molecules number in calibration set : 15

Molecules number in prediction set : 6

Number of the significant descriptors : 97

$$C_0 = 0.6575$$

$$C_1 = 0.9273$$

$D_1 = \text{ARC}$ (100·Average atomic one-electron reaction index for C atoms) ($U = 1000$)

$$C_2 = 0.8646$$

$D_2 = \text{XVC}$ (maximum free valance of C atoms at parabolic region) ($U = 935$)

Whereas the quality of correlation is described by the statistical indices :

$$Se = 0.086; r^2 = 0.9573; F = 145.8766; r_{CV}^2 = 0.9308; Q = 0.8067$$

When working with a validation (or prediction) set, PRECLAV uses specific criteria for selecting the significant descriptors by using the class function. The program verifies if, from the point of view of the values of analyzed descriptor, the calibration set (now the reduced calibration set) is a representative sample of the whole molecular set (now the reduced calibration set + the validation set). The selection of descriptors is harsher. In the case when there is a validation/prediction set, from the point of view of the program the characteristics of the equation (coefficients, number and type of predictors) used in prediction and the quality of the prediction for the calibration set are of less importance. What is in this case significant is the correlation between the estimated values and the experimental values of the dependent property for the molecules of the validation/prediction set. In Table 5, there are listed the estimated values (computed by QSAR-2) and the observed values (from Table 1) of the hCA VII inhibitory power for the molecules in the validation set.

In the QSAR-2, I can state that the program has calculated for the molecules in the validation set values close to the experimental ones and has ordered the molecules in a sequence similar enough to the real one. From the practical point of view, the labeling “high value of dependent property” and “low value of dependent property” is very important, a labeling that the program is always making for the molecules in the validation/prediction set. In Table 5, the calculated values identified by the program as “high” have been marked in bold letters, while the values identified as “low” have been underlined. Of the one molecule labeled as “high value”, are

Table 5. Experimental/calculated values of hCA VII inhibitory activity for the molecules in the validation set

Compd. no.	Obs.	Est.
21	0.0458	-0.006
16	-0.9294	-0.682
4	-0.8573	-0.85
1	-0.7924	-0.853
19	-0.3979	-0.908
6	-0.8808	-0.95

the molecules that also have the highest experimental values of hCA VII inhibitory activity. The two molecules labeled as "low value" two are the molecules that have the lowest experimental hCA VII value. This result, qualitatively correct, suggests that, in a QSAR analysis with prediction set, the program will identify with sufficient accuracy the molecules "suggested for synthesis".

Experimental

The inhibition data for the cytosolic isozyme VII as K_1 (nm) hCA VII were taken from the earlier report¹³ and used after converting them into negative logarithmic units, i.e. I used as $-\log K_1$ (hCA VII).

Quantum chemical descriptor : All the quantum chemical descriptor were calculated from the MOPAC¹¹ and PRECLAV¹² software.

Regression analysis : All the regression analysis was performed using the PRECLAV¹² software.

Conclusions :

Statistically significant QSAR models were generated with the purpose of deriving structural requirements for some newly synthesized, non homologous series of hCA VII inhibitor lead to the following conclusion :

- The molecular features are useful in describing the variation of the dependent property.

- The presence of CH₃ (Compd. no. 18, 19, 21), C₇H₃NSO (Compd. no. 18) and O atom (Compd. no. 21) fragments are favorable to the inhibitory activity.

- The presence of fragment C₇H₄NO (Comp. no. 20) is leads to decreases of the inhibitory activity.

- The percent of sulfur minimum charge for sulphur atom play dominating role on the inhibitory activity.

- The maximum free valance of C atoms which depends on the sum of the bond orders of carbon atoms are

significant to inhibitory activity.

- The tests set using as a validation set suggest that PRECLAV is capable to identify with sufficient accuracy the new, as yet non-synthesized, molecules with higher lower values of the dependent property, included in a prediction set.

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